

Modelling of a Vibro-Impact Power Take-Off Mechanism for Wave Energy Systems

Bingyong Guo and John V. Ringwood

Abstract—One main challenge of wave energy conversion techniques is to design a highly-efficient and cost-effective power take-off (PTO) device which can generate electricity and implement control actions. However, current PTO devices are typically characterised by large peak-to-average power ratios, which requires extra control design to limit power peaks in the time-domain and extra effort to improve power quality at the grid connection point. This paper proposes a non-linear vibro-impact PTO mechanism for a heaving point absorber which can be tuned and detuned under moderate and more extreme sea states. A mathematical model for the vibro-impact mechanism is derived, and intensive numerical simulations are conducted with regular waves, illustrating that the vibro-impact PTO mechanism exhibits a characteristics of band-pass effect and low peak-to-average power ratio. Therefore, a properly designed vibro-impact PTO mechanism has the potential to improve power absorption under moderate sea states, to extend the power production region under more aggressive sea states, and to ease the grid connection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Current research and development activities of wave energy conversion mainly focus on generating electricity from ocean waves and connecting the generated electricity to power grids. However, wave energy converters (WECs) are typically characterised by large peak-to-average power ratios, which can be up to 26.9 in sea testing [1]. Large peak-to-average power ratios are one of the greatest challenges for grid connections. It introduces challenges to the design of highly-efficient and cost-effective power take-off (PTO) devices, while also producing poor power quality at the grid connection point due to large power fluctuations and, hence, extra efforts are required to smooth the generated power. Meanwhile, the frequency of ocean waves varies over time with a range control strategies developed and applied to maximise power absorption of WECs [2] across a broad frequency range. Unfortunately, control action further exaggerates the peak-to-average power ratio. For conventional control methods, such as latching or phase control, reactive or complex-conjugate control [3], a large average extracted power also indicates a large peak-to-average power ratio. Therefore, control strategies should consider limiting the peak-to-average power ratio as a key factor, and a peak-shaving control method is studied in [4] which aims to improve average power absorption and to limit peak-to-average power ratio simultaneously.

Bingyong Guo and John V. Ringwood are with the Centre for Ocean Energy Research, Department of Electronic Engineering, Maynooth University, Maynooth, Ireland, Bingyong.Guo@mu.ie, John.Ringwood@mu.ie.

Some novel concepts in PTO design have the potential to achieve high average power absorption while maintaining low peak-to-average power ratio. A “negative” spring, termed WaveSpring, is developed and tested by CorPower Ocean to increase WEC system’s response bandwidth [5], whose principle is the same as the bi-stable mechanical system with two symmetrically oblique springs to achieve a snap-through mechanism [6]. In addition to non-linear springs, non-linear dampers are studied numerically and experimentally in [7]. These studies conclude that a properly designed non-linear mechanism in the PTO system has the potential to enhance average power absorption of WECs. However, the peak-to-average power ratio is not the focus in these studies.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of a heaving point absorber integrated with a vibro-impact PTO system.

This work proposes a vibro-impact PTO mechanism integrated inside a heaving point absorber. As shown in Fig. 1, a floating buoy (M_b) oscillates under the excitation of incident waves. An inner mass (M_m) is connected to the buoy by a primary spring (k_1) and a linear damper (c), and oscillates accordingly due to the interaction force with the floater. The key mechanism of the vibro-impact PTO is that the secondary (k_2) and tertiary springs (k_3) attached to the top ceiling and floor of the buoy provide impacts when the relative displacement between the inner mass and buoy exceeds the the gaps G_1 and G_2 (positive parameters defined at the equilibrium point), respectively. The vibro-impact events are non-linear and non-smooth, but have the capability to enhance the point absorber’s average power absorption and to reduce the peak-to-average power ratio simultaneously. In this paper, a mathematical model for the vibro-impact PTO

is derived and intensive parametric studies are conducted to understand how design parameters, such as the inner mass and spring stiffness, influence the WEC dynamics and power absorption under regular wave conditions. Irregular wave conditions are not considered here as they will introduce extra complexity to the non-linear dynamics of the vibro-impact mechanism. The hydrodynamic properties of the wave-buoy interaction is computed by a boundary element method code NEMOH [8]. System identification techniques are then applied to approximate the radiation and excitation forces so that a piece-wise linear state space model of the heaving point absorber with vibro-impact PTO mechanism can be derived. The paper will demonstrate that, for this novel PTO system:

- The peak-to-average power ratio is low, which can ease the design of highly-efficient PTO system and the connection to power grids.
- The response amplitude operator (RAO) of the relative motion between the buoy and inner mass acts like a “band-pass filter”, with relatively small gain values when the wave frequency is low. As extreme sea states are characterised by low frequency, the vibro-impact PTO system is inherently decoupled and shows high reliability and survivability under extreme sea states.
- The non-linear dynamics and power absorption of the vibro-impact PTO system can be further optimised according to specific sea states for a given buoy geometry, by adjusting the stiffness, gap, damper and inner mass, to enhance the average extracted power and energy absorption bandwidth.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II details the mathematical modelling of the heaving point absorber with vibro-impact PTO device. Parametric studies and numerical results are discussed in Sections III and IV by varying the inner mass and secondary/tertiary stiffness, respectively. Conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. MODELLING OF VIBRO-IMPACT POWER TAKE-OFF MECHANISM

In this section, for the heaving point absorber with vibro-impact PTO system shown in Fig. 1, a mathematical model is derived for numerical simulation, including the buoy-mass and wave-buoy interactions.

A. Equation of motion

From Fig. 1, the motion of the buoy is described by

$$M_b \ddot{z}_b = f_e + f_r + f_{hs} + f_{pto}, \quad (1)$$

where f_e , f_r and f_{hs} represent the excitation, radiation and hydrostatic forces, respectively. f_{pto} represents the PTO force between the floating buoy and the inner mass. z_b is the heaving displacement of the buoy, \ddot{z}_b represents its acceleration, and M_b is the floater’s mass. For simplicity, only the heave motion is investigated with its positive direction defined upward, and the mooring force is omitted here.

For the inner mass, its equation of motion is written as

$$M_m \ddot{z}_m = -f_{pto}, \quad (2)$$

where M_m , z_m and \ddot{z}_m represent the inner mass, its displacement and acceleration in heave, respectively. The interaction force f_{pto} depends on the relative displacement between the inner mass and the floating buoy, with three possible cases: (i) When the relative displacement is within the two gaps, only the primary spring with stiffness k_1 and the PTO damper with coefficient c are active. (ii) When the relative displacement is positive and larger than the up gap G_1 , the secondary spring with stiffness k_2 is contacted by the inner mass. (iii) When the negative relative displacement exceeds the bottom gap G_2 , the tertiary spring with stiffness k_3 is contacted by the inner mass. Therefore, the PTO force can be summarised as

$$f_{pto} = \begin{cases} k_1 z_r + k_2(z_r - G_1) + cv_r, & z_r \geq G_1, \\ k_1 z_r + cv_r, & G_1 > z_r > -G_2, \\ k_1 z_r + k_3(z_r + G_2) + cv_r, & z_r \leq -G_2, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $z_r = z_m - z_b$ and $v_r = \dot{z}_r$ represent the relative displacement and velocity, respectively.

For a vertical cylinder, the hydrostatic force is given as

$$f_{hs} = -\rho g \pi r^2 z_b, \quad (4)$$

where ρ , g and r are the water density, gravity constant and buoy radius, respectively. The radiation force, in the time-domain, is given as

$$f_r = -m_\infty \ddot{z}_b - k_r * \dot{z}_b, \quad (5)$$

where m_∞ is the added mass at infinite frequency and k_r is the impulse response function (IRF) of the radiation force. The symbol $*$ represents the convolution operator. The excitation force f_e is viewed as the system input in this work and can be determined quantitatively by its frequency response function (FRF), represented as

$$F_e(j\omega) = H_e(j\omega)A(j\omega), \quad (6)$$

where $H_e(j\omega)$ is the FRF of the excitation force and $A(j\omega)$ is the frequency-domain representation of incident wave $\eta(t)$.

B. Wave-buoy interaction

In this work, a general cylindrical buoy is utilised, of $r = 1$ m in radius, $h = 2$ m in height, and $d = 1$ m in draft ($M_m + M_b = M_t = \rho \pi r^2 d$ is applied to constrain the draft at the equilibrium point), and the motion is constrained to heave only as the main focus of this study is on the dynamics of the vibro-impact PTO mechanism. The hydrodynamic coefficients are computed by solving a boundary value problem in the boundary element method code NEMOH [8], and the radiation IRF and the excitation FRF are given in Figs. 2(a)-(b), respectively. In Fig. 2(b), the excitation FRF is represented by its amplitude response $|H_e(j\omega)|$ and phase response $\angle H_e(j\omega)$. The convolution operation in Eq. (5) and the excitation FRF are inconvenient for analysing non-linear dynamics of the heaving point absorber with vibro-impact PTO system, and hence state space models with finite order are derived by system identification techniques to approximate the radiation and excitation forces, detailed in the following two subsections.

Fig. 2. Radiation IRF and excitation FRF computed by NEMOH. The excitation FRF is represented by its amplitude response $|H_e(j\omega)|$ and phase response $\angle H_e(j\omega)$.

C. Radiation force approximation

Here we define f_{rc} representing the convolution term of the radiation fore in Eq. (5), given as

$$f_{rc} = k_r * \dot{z}_b. \quad (7)$$

Finite order approximations of the radiation force were studied in [9], [10], and just an overview is given here. The convolution term can be approximated by

$$\dot{x}_r = A_r x_r + B_r \dot{z}_b, \quad (8)$$

$$f_{rc} \approx C_r x_r, \quad (9)$$

where $x_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ is the state vector for the identified system. $A_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, $C_r \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ are the system matrices. n is the dynamical order which is selected by trial and error in terms of goodness of fit defined by normalised mean square-error [9]. In this study $n = 4$ is used, giving a fit of 0.9998, and the system matrices are given in the Appendix.

Fig. 3. IRFs to represent the convolution term of the ration force.

D. Excitation force approximation

The excitation force can be identified from its FRF which has been modelled numerically and validated experimentally in [11], [12]. Hence, only a brief overview of excitation force approximation is given. In the frequency-domain, the excitation force is expressed in Eq. (6). Alternatively, the excitation force can be expressed in the time-domain, as

$$f_e(t) = k_e(t) * \eta(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k_e(t - \tau) \eta(\tau) d\tau, \quad (10)$$

where $k_e(t)$ is the excitation force IRF related to its FRF $H_e(j\omega)$, given as

$$k_e(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_e(j\omega) e^{j\omega t} d\omega. \quad (11)$$

Based on NEMOH's results in Fig. 2(b), the excitation kernel function $k_e(t)$ is represented by the black dash-dot curve in Fig. 4. However, $k_e(t)$ is non-causal since $k_e(t) \neq 0$ for $t < 0$ (see the shadowed area in Fig. 4). Therefore, a time-shifting technique is applied to causalise the non-causal kernel function $k_e(t)$ to its causalised form $k_{e,c}(t)$ with causalisation time t_c ($t_c \geq 0$). Thus, wave elevation prediction, with a prediction horizon of t_c , is required.

Fig. 4. Comparison of IRFs between the non-causal, causalised and identified wave-to-excitation-force process.

According to the convolution property, this causalised system with wave prediction gives the same excitation force of the non-causal system, since

$$f_e(t) = k_e(t) * \eta(t) = k_{e,c}(t) * \eta_p(t), \quad (12)$$

where $k_{e,c}(t) = k_e(t - t_c)$ and $\eta_p(t) = \eta(t + t_c)$ are the causalised IRF of the excitation force (see the red solid curve in Fig. 4) and the predicted wave elevation advanced by t_c , respectively. The procedures to identify $k_{e,c}(t)$ and to predict $\eta_p(t)$ are detailed in [11], [12].

In this study, Eq. (12) is approximated by the following state-space model

$$\dot{x}_e = A_e x_e + B_e \eta_p, \quad (13)$$

$$f_e \approx C_e x_e + D_e \eta_p, \quad (14)$$

where $x_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ is the state vector for the excitation system. $A_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, $C_e \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ and $D_e \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$ are the system matrices, and n is the order. t_c and n are selected by trial and error in terms of truncation error and goodness

of fit, as defined in [12]. In this study, $t_c = 3.2$ s and $n = 6$ are selected and the identified IRF is compared with the causalised IRF in Fig. 4 with a truncation error of less than 0.0073 and a goodness of fit of 0.9953.

III. INFLUENCE OF INNER MASS

The non-linear dynamics of the vibro-impact PTO are sensitive to design parameters, including M_m , k_1 , k_2 , k_3 , G_1 , G_2 , and c , and incident waves in terms of wave height H and frequency ω . In this section, parametric studies are conducted by varying the inner mass from 200 kg to 3,000 kg, subjected to harmonic waves with height $H = 0.8$ m and frequency ω varying from 0.06 rad/s to 6.28 rad/s. To evaluate the dynamics of the heaving point absorber with vibro-impact PTO, the relative RAO is defined as

$$RAO_r = \frac{2|z_r|}{H}. \quad (15)$$

To evaluate the performance of the vibro-impact PTO mechanism, the instantaneous power P_i , average power P_a and peak-to-average power ratio P_{p2a} are defined as

$$P_i = cv_r^2, \quad (16)$$

$$P_a = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T P_i dt, \quad (17)$$

$$P_{p2a} = \frac{\max(P_i)}{P_a}, \quad (18)$$

where T is the wave period.

Fig. 5. Comparison of relative RAOs under a wide range of inner mass variation as the wave frequency increases in (a), and decreases in (b). The results in the red solid rectangle are larger than their counterparts in the red dash rectangle. Four points P1-P4 are marked by red dots and their time traces are compared in Fig. 7.

The relative RAO between the inner mass and the buoy is given in Fig. 5, considering a wide range of inner mass variation and wave frequency fluctuation. In Fig. 5(a), wave frequency increases from 0.06 rad/s to 6.28 rad/s, whilst it decreases from 6.28 rad/s to 0.06 rad/s in Fig. 5(b). Both Figs. 5(a) and (b) indicate that: (i) The relative RAO has a characteristic typical of a band-pass filter, with a small gain when $\omega < 1$ rad/s or $\omega > 3.5$ rad/s, and a large gain when the wave frequency is close to the resonance frequency region. The maximum relative RAO rises to 4.5 in Fig. 5(a). (ii) The resonance frequency decreases from 2.5 rad/s to 1.5 rad/s as the inner mass increases from 200 kg to 3000 kg. That is, a larger inner mass results in a lower resonance

frequency. (iii) When the wave frequency is close to the resonance frequency region (especially in the areas marked by red solid/dash rectangles), the relative RAO in Fig. 5(a) is much larger than its counterpart in Fig. 5(b), indicating the existence of multi-stability.

In this work, the performance of the vibro-impact PTO mechanism is evaluated by the average power P_a and peak-to-average power ratio P_{p2a} , defined in Eqs. (17) and (18), respectively. Under a wide range of inner mass variation, contour plots of the average power and peak-to-average power ratio are given in Fig. 6, with wave frequency increasing in Figs. 6(a)-(b), and decreasing in Figs. 6(c)-(d). Fig. 6 illustrates that: (i) Figs. 6(a) and (c) show the band-pass characteristics of the average power, with very low power output at a low or high frequency, and with high power output when the wave frequency is close to the device resonant frequency. (ii) In Figs. 6(b) and (d), the peak-to-average power ratio is small, varying from 1.5 to 3.5. This is one advantage of the vibro-impact PTO mechanism, which can ease the design of highly-efficient and cost-effective PTO device, and connecting wave power to the grid. (iii) The maximum values of average power in Figs. 6(a) and (c) do not necessarily indicate maximum values of peak-to-average power ratio in Figs. 6(b) and (d), respectively. (iv) Figs. 6(a) and (c) show a high accordance with Figs. 5(a) and (b), respectively. That is, a larger relative RAO also means a larger average power capture. (v) Comparing Figs. 6(a)-(b) with Figs. 6(c)-(d) correspondingly, it also indicates that the performance of the vibro-impact PTO is sensitive to initial conditions due to multi-stability.

Fig. 6. Contour plots of the average power and peak-to-average power ratio with wave frequency increasing in (a)-(b), and decreasing in (c)-(d). The results in the red solid rectangles are larger than their counterparts in the red dash rectangles, and the time series of the red dots marked P1-P4 are compared in Fig. 7.

The relative motion is typical of band-pass characteristics, which can be an advantage of the vibro-impact PTO mechanism to match a specific wave spectrum via design optimisation. It also can be used to improve device survivability under extreme sea states, as large waves normally occur at low frequency and the vibro-impact PTO system is automatically detuned. To address the band-pass effect and multi-stability of the vibro-impact PTO device, four simulation conditions marked by red dots P1-P4 in Figs. 5 and 6 are selected to compare their time traces in Figs. 7(a)-(d), with simulation conditions of $\omega = 0.8$ rad/s, $\omega = 1.9$ rad/s, $\omega = 1.9$ rad/s and $\omega = 3$ rad/s, respectively. The inner mass is $M_m = 2,100$ kg and other simulation conditions are given in the Appendix. Zero initial conditions are applied in Fig. 7(a), (c) and (d), whilst the initial conditions for Fig. 7(b) are $[z_{b0}, \dot{z}_{b0}, z_{m0}, \dot{z}_{m0}]' = [-0.5, 0, 0.5, 5]'$. In Fig. 7(a), the buoy, inner mass and relative displacements are small and, consequently, the instantaneous and average power outputs are small. The average power is less than 1 W, which means that the vibro-impact PTO mechanism is inherently fully decoupled. This shows that the vibro-impact PTO has the potential to improve its survivability and reliability under extreme sea states which is typically characterised by low frequency. Comparing the results in Figs. 7(b) and (c), the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact PTO system are sensitive to initial conditions due to multi-stability. In Fig. 7(d), the buoy and inner mass motions are small, but the relative motion is slightly larger as there exists a large phase shift between motions of the buoy and inner mass, resulting in larger instantaneous and average power outputs than those in Fig. 7(a).

As shown in Fig. 7(b), the amplitude of the relative displacement is about 1.6 m while the physical constraint is 1 m (half the buoy height). Hence, design optimisation is required to limit the relative motion, such as increasing the buoy's height, the stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs, or decreasing the impact gaps. In the following section, the influence of the secondary and tertiary stiffness on the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact PTO system are discussed.

IV. INFLUENCE OF SPRING STIFFNESS

The relative motion can be constrained by increasing the stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs, and this effect is now discussed. Fig. 8 illustrates the relative RAO with varying stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs. The black solid curve represents the simulation results with $k_2 = k_3 = 0$ N/m, in which vibro-impact events have no effect. The red dash and blue dot curves represent the simulation results with small stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs at $k_2 = k_3 = 20,000$ N/m with respect to the frequency increasing and decreasing cases, respectively. The pink dash-dot and olive dash-dot-dot curves represent the simulation results with large stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs, for $k_2 = k_3 = 200,000$ N/m with respect to the frequency increasing and decreasing cases, respectively. The physical constraint is given in a cyan short-dash line.

Fig. 7. Time traces of the buoy, mass and relative displacements, instantaneous and average power outputs, with (a)-(d) representing the time traces for the points P1-P4 in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. The simulation conditions are $w = 0.8$ rad/s for (a), $w = 1.9$ rad/s for (b)-(c), and $w = 3$ rad/s for (d), with $M_i = 2100$ kg and other parameters given in the Appendix. The initial conditions are $[z_{b0}, \dot{z}_{b0}, z_{m0}, \dot{z}_{m0}]' = [-0.5, 0, 0.5, 5]'$ for (b) and zero initial conditions are used for (a), (b) and (d).

Fig. 8. (a) Relative RAOs with various stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs. The black solid, red dash, blue dot, pink dash-dot, and olive dash-dot-dot curves represent the results at $k_2 = k_3 = 0$ N/m, $k_2 = k_3 = 20,000$ N/m with increasing and decreasing frequency, respectively, and $k_2 = k_3 = 200,000$ N/m with increasing and decreasing frequency, respectively. The cyan short-dash curve represent the physical constraint.

As shown in Fig. 8, the trends of relative RAOs show different characteristics when the frequency increases and decreases. For the simulation with relatively large stiffness of $k_2 = k_3 = 200,000$ N/m, the relative RAO approaching route is $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow F$ as the frequency increases, whilst the route is $F \rightarrow E \rightarrow C \rightarrow B \rightarrow A$ as the frequency decreases. Therefore, multi-stability exists within the frequency range between points C and E. Comparing the red dash curve with the pink dash-dot curve, it can be seen that the relative motion can be constrained effectively by increasing the stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs. Meanwhile, the bandwidth is extended. Therefore, a larger stiffness value for the secondary and tertiary springs is preferred to limit the relative motion and enlarge the bandwidth.

V. CONCLUSION

This study proposes a vibro-impact PTO mechanism for a heaving point absorber, with specific foci on its mathematical model and non-linear dynamics. Numerical simulations are conducted by varying the inner mass, spring stiffness of the secondary and tertiary springs, and the wave frequency. Numerical results show that the vibro-impact PTO mechanism is characterised by a band-pass effect and, therefore, it is automatically detuned under extreme sea states, normally characterised by low frequencies. Numerical studies also conclude that the peak-to-average power ratio of the vibro-impact PTO device is low, varying from 1.5 to 3.5, under a wide range of inner mass and wave frequency variations. These two properties of the vibro-impact PTO mechanism have the potential to improve system survivability under extreme sea states, to enhance power capture bandwidth under moderate sea states, and to ease grid connections.

The non-linear dynamics of the vibro-impact PTO system are sensitive to design parameters, and hence design optimisation is required. Ongoing work focuses on parametric studies of the design parameters by varying the inner mass, spring stiffness, impact gaps and PTO damping coefficient over a wide range to provide guidelines for prototype design.

APPENDIX

Simulation conditions are: buoy radius $r = 1$ m, height $h = 2$ m, draft $d = 1$ m, total mass of the buoy and inner mass $M_t = M_b + M_m = 3,220.13$ kg, water density $\rho = 1,025$ kg/m³, gravity constant $g = 9.81$ N/kg, added mass at infinite frequency $m_\infty = 1,883.47$ kg, the spring stiffness $k_1 = 5,000$ N/m, $k_2 = k_3 = 20,000$ N/m, the PTO damping coefficient $c = 1,000$ Ns/m, impact gaps $G_1 = G_2 = 0.8$ m and wave height $H = 0.8$ m. The inner mass M_m and wave frequency ω are varied in parametric studies and given in the caption of each figure.

The system matrices for the identified radiation subsystem in Eqs. (8) and (9) are

$$A_r = \begin{bmatrix} -1.50, -2.06, 1.54, -0.35 \\ 2.06, -0.01, 0.07, -0.02 \\ -1.54, 0.07, -2.38, 1.96 \\ -0.35, 0.02, -1.96, -0.54 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B_r = \begin{bmatrix} -403.88, 22.57, -181.05, -49.82 \end{bmatrix}',$$

$$C_r = \begin{bmatrix} -4.04, -0.23, 1.81, -0.50 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The system matrices of the identified excitation force in Eqs. (13) and (14) are

$$A_e = \begin{bmatrix} -0.05, -0.61, -0.13, -0.24, -0.13, -0.12 \\ 0.61, -0.19, -1.13, -0.29, -0.39, -0.24 \\ -0.13, 1.13, -0.39, -1.56, -0.47, -0.52 \\ 0.24, -0.29, 1.56, -0.62, -2.04, -0.66 \\ -0.13, 0.39, -0.47, 2.04, -0.88, -2.38 \\ 0.12, -0.24, 0.52, -0.66, 2.38, -1.21 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B_e = \begin{bmatrix} -549.4, 884.3, -1008.7, 939.5, -784.6, 603.3 \end{bmatrix}',$$

$$C_e = \begin{bmatrix} -5.49, -8.84, -10.09, -9.39, -7.85, -6.03 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$D_e = \begin{bmatrix} 49.85 \end{bmatrix}.$$

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 841388. This paper reflects only the authors' view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Sjolte, I. Bjerke, A. Crozier, G. Tjensvoll, and M. Molinas, "All-electric wave energy power take off system with improved power quality at the grid connection point," in *Proc. Transmission and Distribution Conference and Exposition*, Orlando, USA, 2012, pp. 1–7.
- [2] J. V. Ringwood, G. Bacelli, and F. Fusco, "Energy-maximizing control of wave-energy converters: The development of control system technology to optimize their operation," *IEEE Control Syst. Mag.*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 30–55, 2014.
- [3] J. Falnes, *Ocean waves and oscillating systems: linear interactions including wave-energy extraction*. Cambridge university press, 2002.
- [4] J. Henriques, L. Gato, J. Lemos, R. Gomes, and A. Falcão, "Peak-power control of a grid-integrated oscillating water column wave energy converter," *Energy*, vol. 109, pp. 378–390, 2016.
- [5] J. H. Todalshaug, G. S. Ásgeirsson, E. Hjalmarsson, J. Maillet, P. Möller, P. Pires, M. Guérinel, and M. Lopes, "Tank testing of an inherently phase-controlled wave energy converter," *Int. J. Mar. Energy*, vol. 15, pp. 68–84, 2016.
- [6] X. Zhang, J. Yang, and L. Xiao, "Numerical study of an oscillating wave energy converter with nonlinear snap-through power-take-off systems in regular waves," *J. Ocean Wind Energy*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 225–230, 2014.
- [7] H. Bailey, "Influence of a nonlinear power take off on a wave energy converter," Ph.D. dissertation, PhD thesis, The University of Edinburgh, 2010.
- [8] A. Babarit and G. Delhommeau, "Theoretical and numerical aspects of the open source BEM solver NEMOH," in *Proc. EWTEC*, Nantes, France, 2015, pp. 6–11.
- [9] B. Guo, R. Patton, S. Jin, J. Gilbert, and D. Parsons, "Nonlinear modeling and verification of a heaving point absorber for wave energy conversion," *IEEE T. Sustain. Energ.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 453–461, 2017.
- [10] N. Faedo, Y. Peña-Sanchez, and J. V. Ringwood, "Finite-order hydrodynamic model determination for wave energy applications using moment-matching," *Ocean Eng.*, vol. 163, pp. 251–263, 2018.
- [11] B. Guo, R. Patton, and S. Jin, "Identification and validation of excitation force for a heaving point absorber wave energy converter," in *Proc. EWTEC*, Cork, Ireland, 2017, pp. 1–9.
- [12] B. Guo, R. J. Patton, S. Jin, and J. Lan, "Numerical and experimental studies of excitation force approximation for wave energy conversion," *Renew. Energ.*, vol. 125, pp. 877–889, 2018.